

THE IMPORTANCE OF MUSIC THEORY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8289303>

Abstract. *The article focuses mainly on the theory and system of music, musical sound and its characteristics, the art of music and its characteristics, as well as the main expressive means of music, artistic image.*

Key words: *musical busyness, hardness, extension, timbre, musical system, octave musical system.*

ВАЖНОСТЬ ТЕОРИИ МУЗЫКИ

Аннотация. *В статье основное внимание уделяется теории и системе музыки, музыкальному звучанию и его характеристикам, музыкальному искусству и его особенностям, а также основным выразительным средствам музыки, художественному образу.*

Ключевые слова: *музыкальная занятость, твердость, протяженность, тембр, музыкальный строй, октавный музыкальный строй.*

Being able to "read" the content of any piece of music, understand it, and To "see" how it is structured, avalom, to know the language of music, musical it is necessary to develop the ability to think.

"Musical language" means the means of musical expressiveness and imagery the system found is. The tools of the musical language are the structural elements of music is considered These are pitch, length, meter, rhythm, interval, chord, key, tools such as tonality and melody. Elements of music and their relationship Education about music theory is described in the subjects of music theory. Musicology is a branch of art studies. He, in turn, is as follows covers the fields of knowledge: music theory, music history, musical ethnography, musical criticism, musical acoustics, musical psychology and other fields. Ifedjio consists of such subjects as musical instruments; and studies music from a theoretical point of view. The general task of these disciplines is to help in the perception of music, its understanding, its potential, and its impact on listeners. These subjects are future music teachersiii. plays an important role in preparation. They have the secrets of music not only for their musical needs, but also the necessary knowledge and skills it is necessary for future students to master it in order to remember it.

The initial part of the system of sciences about the theory of music is Music. The basics of the theory - the main elements of music and especially the melody and its makes it a task to learn its features. Acquired knowledge learning about each musical element in order to generalize despite the fact that they are included in separate chapters of the manuals, the reader is aware of this it is necessary to keep in mind that the elements of music are their own only in relation to each other can show expressive features.

The content of art is life, the reality around us, man and his inner world - thoughts, feelings. Art is more than other types of human activity absorbs reality by creating artistic images. That person's feelings and it supposedly creates the world anew in a form that directly affects consciousness. But, an artist does not copy life, events and things. He is an image sorting out the

most common, typical features and all of them after understanding it, he changes the shape of the image, and then turns it into a painting, a poem, a piece of music embodies in the form of Of course, the author of any artist's work is a person keeps its complexity within itself. Because it is the objective material of the external world it is reworked separately in the mind of the artist and becomes an original, unique creation reborn. However, at the same time, every creative work is public consciousness is also considered a product. Because it is a certain social psychology, the country will be associated with a historical event. The social aspect of artistic creativity then it is shown that a person is aware of his contemporaries and his people's past and He feels his connection with humanity through artistic images. True art is eternal while creating artistic values, it also realizes the continuous connection of the visuals increases.

Thus, works of art are pictures of both life and creativity. But types of art are able to depict different aspects of life equally it's not. Each type of art is distinguished by its own means and principles of expression stands So, what is the art of music? What are its goals and tasks?

Music* is the art of tone (intonation), reality expressed in sounds is an artistic reflection. It reflects existence in its own way, enriches it, and understands it helps to get and change 0. It is known that music plays an important role in society Music - (Greek - jiouoixii) - the art of the fairies. plays. Music is a way of life and social life of a person, entertainment and recreation It serves as a sign that will definitely be present in your life, making a person spiritual is a unique tool that achieves values. It is the spiritual and moral world of a person It is considered an effective tool of aesthetic education that forms its goals is considered Music itself, its creators, performers, and listeners. Music culture is an important area in society's culture.

There is no doubt that music has a close relationship with other forms of art. The musical intonation basis of their live communication is close to literature, rhythmic organization is similar to poetry and dance art, proportionality of his works its structure is seen in accordance with architectural forms. Add to that It should be noted that works of literature, fine art, and sculpture are often musical works serves as a basis for Music has one or another meaning that is revealed through musical images will be These are natural scenes, events and situations in social life, human is the inner spiritual world. Music can express a person's feelings and mood.

At the same time, he describes nature scenes, action images.

It also has the ability to embody, to imitate the sincere sounds of life (chirping birds, thunder).

Sound is a physical phenomenon. On the other hand, the concept of "sound" is several more it includes a chain of various events that are organically connected. The sound source is one are the oscillating motions of an object (for example, a wire string). As a result of such actions, sound waves occur in the air. And they are affecting the auditory organ, the sound passes through the auditory nerve to the brain creates intuition.

In nature, the sounds that can be played by the human quioq are endless. They are noisy' - natural sounds such as knocking, rustling, hissing, and musical – singing Loud sounds are also used in musical works. For example: circles, drums, drums, cymbals, cymbals. to artificial sounds such as the human voice and the sound of a musical instrument Musical sound is the main tool of the art of music and the surroundings serves to reflect reality. They are centuries-old musical culture sorted out in the process of development and organized into a specific system.

The basis of the elements of musical expressiveness is the musical sound itself features. These characteristics are the speed of vibration of the oscillating body, vibration width, vibration duration, and its components in terms of quantity and quality comes out. The volume of sound depends on the speed of vibration. What is the rate of oscillation? the larger, the higher the pitch, and vice versa, the faster the vibration the smaller it is, the lower the pitch. That is why, sounds are divided into two groups:

- 1) sounds with clearly defined pitch - musical sounds;
- 2) sounds of uncertain pitch - noisy sounds.

The strength of the vibration is the amplitude of the vibration is expressed and provides a solid sound (fortc-piano sound). Vibrations the wider the amplitude, the louder the sound.

The duration of the vibration depends on the length of the sound.

The wider the amplitude of the vibrations, the longer the sound continues.

The composition of sound source vibrations should be understood as follows, The sound source is simultaneously not only as a whole, but also in parts also vibrates. Its whole vibration is considered the main vibration and is the best produces an audible sound. This sound is called the main tone. Each department Half, one-third, one-fourth, one-fifth of the total length of the part the speed of vibration of one, etc.) creates a sound corresponding to its length. Such additional sound is heard two or three times higher than the main tone.

Because the shorter the length of the sound source, the faster its vibration slmn increases and the resulting sound pitch increases. These additions are called tonal overtones or overtones.

So, the overtones included in the composition of the sound represent the variety of the sound, i.e creates a timbre feature. Timbre is an individual quality of sound, other emphasizes that they do not resemble sounds.

These four features are definitely manifested in every musical sound.

The musical system was in a certain relationship in terms of pitch.

The sounds consist of a series of sounds that increase in pitch or.

The sequential arrangement of the musical system in descending order is called the scale.

Each sound of the speaker is called its pitch. (The order of the step the number is represented by a Roman numeral).

The stages of the musical sound system are the main and secondary stages separate The main steps are seven boiib, independent names and Latin allfbonlng has the letter The names of the main steps are all the main ones of the entire vocal range It is repeated periodically to cover the steps. This is the case the eighth sound depends on the first overtone of the main tone. First overtone pitch (oscillating frequency) is twice as high as the fundamental pitch it becomes rich and harmonious with it.

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